

A Compact, Self-Recovering Wire Electrode Electrohydrodynamic Pump for High-Speed McKibben Artificial Muscle Actuation

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Soft robotics requires compliant actuators for safe human interaction. While McKibben artificial muscles are popular for their high force output, their reliance on bulky, noisy pumps limits their use in wearable devices. Electrohydrodynamic (EHD) pumps offer a compact and silent alternative, but existing designs struggle with dielectric discharge and fabrication issues, which compromise reliability and power density. This study introduces a novel EHD pump featuring 0.1 mm copper wire electrodes in a diagonal arrangement within a laser-cut acrylic frame. This design improves dielectric resilience, minimizes deformation, and allows for compact integration. A new simplified fabrication process results in sample variation under 5%. The pump demonstrates remarkable performance, achieving 107 kPa pressure and an 88 mL min⁻¹ flowrate, doubling the power density of the previous model while retaining 88% of its flowrate after 50 discharge events. An automated self-recovery mechanism is also implemented, enabling the pump to instantly restore function after a discharge. When paired with a McKibben muscle, the system achieves a 2 s contraction time, a tenfold improvement over the prior EHD-driven system. This work presents a significant advancement in fast, resilient, and scalable actuation, paving the way for next-generation wearable robotics and assistive technologies.

of safe interaction with humans and complex environments.^[1–6] Among its diverse applications, wearable and assistive soft robotic devices have attracted significant attention due to their potential to enhance mobility, rehabilitation, and daily functionality in human-centered settings.^[7–9] A core challenge in such systems is actuation, generating motion in a way that remains compact, lightweight, and responsive. Various actuation strategies have been explored, including pneumatic and hydraulic actuators,^[10–13] dielectric elastomer actuators (DEA),^[14,15] tendon-driven systems,^[16,17] magnetic composites,^[18] ionic polymer-metal composites (IPMC),^[19] and thermo- or chemo-responsive materials.^[20,21] Among these, fluidic actuators are widely used for their simplicity, high force output, and fast response.^[22,23]

A prominent example of fluidic actuators is the McKibben artificial muscle, which is widely used in soft robotics due to its high force-to-weight ratio, mechanical compliance, and ability to mimic the contraction of natural muscle tissue.^[24] These actuators consist of an elastomeric inner tube encased in a braided mesh, which shortens and expands radially when pressurized.^[25] Their inherent softness and high contractile force make them particularly

1. Introduction

Soft robotics has revolutionized the field of robotics by introducing systems that are inherently compliant, adaptable, and capable

contraction of natural muscle tissue.^[24] These actuators consist of an elastomeric inner tube encased in a braided mesh, which shortens and expands radially when pressurized.^[25] Their inherent softness and high contractile force make them particularly

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suitable for wearable and assistive robotic systems that require safe, adaptable interaction with the human body.^[26,27] However, like other fluidic actuator systems, McKibben muscles rely on fluidic pressurization, either through gas compression or liquid pumping. This necessitates the use of bulky external compressors or pumps, introducing challenges related to weight, noise, vibrations, and heat generation. These limitations underscore the need for compact, silent, and mechanically passive pumping technologies that can be seamlessly integrated into next-generation wearable platforms.

Electrohydrodynamic (EHD) pumps have emerged as a promising actuation technology for soft robotics due to their mechanically passive design, which enables fluid motion without moving parts. They offer several advantages, including compact size, lightweight structure, silent operation, negligible heat generation, and reversible flow without valves.^[28–30] EHD pumps operate by applying a high DC voltage across electrodes immersed in a dielectric liquid, producing ion-drift-driven flow through continuous ionization and neutralization processes. The type of charge generated depends on the electrode configuration and the properties of the liquid. In this mechanism, illustrated in **Figure 1a**, liquid molecules acquire negative charges at the cathode, drift toward the anode, and are subsequently neutralized, enabling sustained fluid flow without mechanical components.^[31] A variety of electrode configurations have been investigated for EHD pumps, including planar,^[32] needle-to-ring,^[33] disk,^[34] and triangular prism-to-slit geometries.^[35] Among these, planar electrodes are the most widely adopted owing to their structural symmetry, ease of fabrication, and capability for flow reversibility.^[28,36]

A major challenge in EHD pumps is dielectric discharge. These pumps typically operate at high electric fields, which significantly increases the risk of dielectric discharge. Such discharge can occur in two ways: first, when the applied voltage reaches the dielectric breakdown strength of the liquid; and second, during long-term continuous operation, where the dielectric liquid gradually degrades and its breakdown voltage decreases. In conventional non-resilient EHD pumps, a safety factor must be applied—for example, limiting the operating voltage to about 60%–70% of the breakdown threshold—to avoid even a single discharge, since one event can permanently disable the pump by damaging the insulating material and creating conductive paths that lead to short circuits.^[37] To overcome this limitation, a diagonal electrode design was developed that redirects discharges through the dielectric fluid rather than through the solid structure.^[38] Placing electrodes on opposing surfaces causes discharges to form temporary bubbles in the fluid instead of destructive shorts, allowing the pump to restore function after breakdown events. This resilience allows the pump to operate at a safety factor of 1.0, close to the breakdown voltage, thereby enabling access to maximum fluidic power without the risk of permanent damage. This approach significantly improves the pump's robustness against dielectric breakdown while expanding its operational range.

In our previous work,^[38] an EHD pump incorporating copper sheet electrodes arranged diagonally within flexible layers was introduced, demonstrating 90% performance retention after 100 discharge events. However, its scalability and power density were limited by fabrication constraints. Specifically, the use of

cutting plotters imposed a minimum electrode width of ≈ 1 mm, restricting electrode density. Furthermore, the flexible base deformed under pressure (**Figure 1h**), leading to channel distortion and increased electrode spacing, both of which significantly degraded pumping performance in wider channels. Although an active resilience concept using multiple pumps was demonstrated by alternating voltage between pumps to expel bubbles and restore function in an open fluidic system, it was not implemented in integration with a soft actuator, thereby limiting reliable actuation under practical conditions.

To address these limitations, it is essential to increase the number of electrodes per unit length to improve power density and to minimize pump deformation to maintain performance. This can be achieved by using small-diameter wire electrodes, enabling finer electrode spacing without increasing channel size. Wire-based designs have recently been explored, such as the fiber-shaped EHD pump with helical wire electrodes introduced in.^[31] Using a rigid base material such as acrylic helps prevent pump deformation.^[30] In this study, we propose a novel EHD pump with a planar configuration featuring 0.1 mm diameter wire electrodes arranged diagonally (**Figure 1b,c**). This design improves resilience to dielectric breakdown (**Figure 1d**), retaining 88% of its flowrate after 50 discharge breakdowns (**Figure 1e**), demonstrating high durability against dielectric failure. The electrodes are embedded in a rigid acrylic frame, which prevents swelling and deformation during operation, enabling scalable and consistent performance even in wider channels (**Figure 1f,g**). Despite its rigidity, the pump remains compact and lightweight, with maximum dimensions of $140.6 \times 25 \times 4.5$ mm and a maximum mass of only 17.12 g, making it suitable for portable and wearable applications. To further enhance power density, design optimization was conducted using both mathematical modeling and finite element analysis (FEA) of the electric field. A new simple fabrication method was developed using only laser cutting and widely available materials. The fabrication process demonstrated excellent reliability. The developed pump achieved a maximum pressure of 107 kPa and a maximum flowrate of 88 mL min^{-1} . Compared with the previous resilient EHD pump, the new wire pump design demonstrates substantial improvements in both performance and power density—achieving more than double the power density (131% increase) with respect to channel size and achieving more than a 20% improvement with respect to pump mass (**Figure 1i**).

Additionally, this work introduces a fully automated self-recovery mechanism. By leveraging the pump's self-sensing capability, the system detects discharge events and instantly switches the voltage input, actively removing bubbles and restoring functionality within the same device. This ensures reliable and uninterrupted operation. The self-recovery system consists of the main pump and a small auxiliary bubble-rejector pump. When a discharge occurs in the main pump, the voltage is instantly redirected to the auxiliary pump, which quickly removes the bubbles and restores the main pump's functionality. The mechanism is demonstrated in both continuous flow and soft robotic actuation scenarios, showcasing self-recovering actuation. To validate the practical relevance of the developed system, the optimized EHD pump was integrated with a McKibben artificial muscle. The system exhibited significant performance improvements over previous EHD-driven McKibben muscles,

Figure 1. Wire electrode EHD pump. a) EHD mechanism inside the wire pump, illustrating ionization of the dielectric liquid that induces fluid flow. b) Wire pump dimensions. c) Exploded view of the pump structure, consisting of three layers: upper and lower acrylic layers with integrated copper wire electrodes, and a middle double-sided adhesive layer containing the fluidic channel. d) Discharge resilience mechanism: discharge events generate bubbles without causing permanent damage, and the pump restores operation after bubble removal. e) Flowrate performance under up to 50 dielectric discharge events at various voltages, demonstrating reliability. f,g) Pressure and flowrate scalability for different wire pumps, showing uniform scalability of pressure with the number of electrodes and flowrate with channel size. h) Deformation observed in the previous flexible resilient pump under high pressure, limiting its performance and scalability. i) Comparison between the wire pump and the previous resilient pump, highlighting significant improvements in performance and power density.

achieving a contraction time of 2 s—ten times faster than earlier integrations^[39]—alongside 15% strain and 4.8 N force at zero strain. These results highlight the effectiveness of the proposed pump as a fast response, resilient actuation system, reinforcing its potential for deployment in next-generation wearable robotics and human-assistive technologies.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Design Optimization

To achieve high power density, design optimization is essential. As the pump's pressure and flowrate performance depend on the generated electric field inside the channel,^[40] maximizing the electric field in the flow direction results in the highest fluidic power. The primary geometric parameters of the pump are the electrode spacing a , the pair shift b , the channel height h , and the wire diameter D , as illustrated in the cross-sectional view in **Figure 2a**. In this study, the optimization focused on a and b , which are the dominant parameters influencing the concentration of the electric field along the flow direction. Two approaches were employed: 1) A mathematical modeling approach, in which the derived expressions describe the maximum power density considering the relationships among pressure, flowrate, and geometric factors and 2) an electric field simulation approach using

FEA implemented in COMSOL Multiphysics, where the simulation was performed to maximize the electric field in the flow direction.

Although a and b were the focus of optimization, we note that both h and D are also critical for pump performance. A larger channel height reduces the concentration of the electric field in the flow direction and can induce flow turbulence that decreases performance.^[37] Figure S3a, Supporting Information compares two identical pumps with different channel heights of 0.5 and 1 mm, demonstrating that performance decreases as channel height increases. Based on these considerations, we selected $h = 0.5$ mm, corresponding to the minimum thickness of the adhesive layer used in the fabrication process for the channel. Experimental investigations of D (**Figure 3g,h**) show that thicker wires increase current consumption and reduce efficiency, whereas thinner wires improve performance but are more fragile during fabrication. Considering these trade-offs, a wire diameter of 0.1 mm was selected as optimal for both efficiency and manufacturability. Further details are provided in Note S1, Supporting Information.

The results from both the mathematical model and FEA yield the same optimized value for $b = 1.4$ mm and only a slight difference in the optimal a value: 0.3 mm from the mathematical model and 0.4 mm from the FEA. This small discrepancy arises mainly because FEA accounts for the electric field interactions

Figure 2. Geometry design optimization and fabrication process. a) Cross-sectional geometry of the wire pump with key design parameters. b) Comparison of the performance of the mathematical modeling design and the FEA design at 6.5 kV. c) Winding the wire around the laser-cut acrylic plates as part of the fabrication process. d) Flowrate–voltage curves for five different fabricated samples. e) Pressure–voltage curves for the same samples.

Figure 3. Characteristics of the wire electrode EHD pump. a) Pressure–flowrate curves at different voltages for a pump with 80 electrode pairs and a 4 mm channel width. b) Maximum pressure achieved by the pump with 80 electrode pairs and a 4 mm channel width. c) Pressure–flowrate curves at different voltages for a pump with 20 electrode pairs and a 16 mm channel width. d) Maximum flowrate achieved by the pump with 20 electrode pairs and a 16 mm channel width. e) Response time of 0.4 s. f) Flowrate reversibility under positive and negative voltages for a pump with 20 electrode pairs and a 4 mm channel width. g) Current consumption for different wire diameters with the same pump design. h) Power efficiency for various wire sizes. i) Power efficiency as a function of the applied voltage for a pump with 80 electrode pairs and a 4 mm channel width.

among all electrodes in the domain, whereas the mathematical model considers only the opposing electric field from the nearest neighboring electrode pair.

To validate the optimization results, different pumps were fabricated and tested using a design with ten electrode pairs and 4 mm channel width. A fabricated sample is shown in Figure S4a, Supporting Information. Two designs were compared for

pressure–flowrate performance: one based on the mathematical model and the other on the FEA optimization. The mathematical model design used $a = 0.3$ mm, $b = 1.4$ mm, while the FEA design used $a = 0.4$ mm, $b = 1.4$ mm. For both designs, the maximum fluidic power was measured, and the power density was calculated by dividing the fluidic power by the channel size. The results showed that both designs performed similarly, with

the FEA design exhibiting a slightly higher power density (Figure 2b). Based on these findings, the optimized parameters were determined to be $a = 0.4$ mm and $b = 1.4$ mm. A comparison of flowrate and pressure performance under increasing voltage further confirmed that both methods yield nearly identical results (Figure S3b,c, Supporting Information). These findings validate the effectiveness of the proposed optimization approach and demonstrate that the mathematical design can be reliably used, as it achieves nearly identical performance. Furthermore, additional comparisons with other pump designs confirmed that the selected values deliver the best performance and power density (Figure S4b,c, Supporting Information).

2.2. New Fabrication Method for Wire Pump

The pump consists of three layers (Figure 1c): two acrylic sheets and one double-sided adhesive very high bond (VHB) layer. First, a 2 mm acrylic sheet is laser-cut to form the pump's shape, including guide teeth to assist in winding the wire and ensuring precise dimensions. The laser cutting process consists of three steps: engraving for the copper strip connection, engraving for the wire path, and a final cut for the pump's outer contour. The differences between these steps lie in the laser power and cutting speed, as detailed in Note S3, Supporting Information.

After laser cutting, the acrylic sheets are cleaned, and a small amount of ultraviolet solder mask photosensitive ink is applied to fill the wire grooves, helping to secure the wire in place. High-purity (99.9%) copper wire with a 0.1 mm diameter, is used for pump fabrication. The wire is wound around the acrylic sheet, guided by the grooves along the edges to maintain the designed spacing (Figure 2c). Once the winding process is complete, a copper strip with conductive adhesive is used to connect the wires on both sides, further securing them in place. Any excess wire is trimmed and removed. The two acrylic parts are then exposed to ultraviolet light for 5 min to cure the ink, providing additional stability for the wires.

A 3M VHB double-sided adhesive tape with a thickness of 0.5 mm serves as the middle layer, bonding the two acrylic sheets and securing the wires. The VHB layer includes pre-cut grooves in the center to form the channel. After assembly, tube connectors are attached to the pump, making it ready for use. A detailed fabrication process is presented in Figure S5, Supporting Information. Five different samples were fabricated and tested for flowrate and pressure using the same design, featuring 20 electrode pairs and a 4 mm channel width, as shown in Figure 2d,e. The maximum coefficient of variation was 4.98% for the flowrate and 1.63% for the pressure. These results confirm that the fabrication process is reliable.

2.3. Performance Analysis

The introduced pump features a completely new structure based on a planar diagonal wire electrode EHD pump. A performance analysis is required to evaluate the pump's output and characteristics. For this purpose, different pumps, based on the optimized design values discussed above and varying in size, were fabricated and tested. Figure 3a presents the pressure-flowrate curves for different applied voltages for the pump with 80 pairs and

4 mm channel width. The results show a clear trend where increasing the voltage enhances both pressure and flowrate, demonstrating the expected EHD pumping behavior. The maximum achieved pressure is 107 kPa, as shown in Figure 3b. Similarly, other pump with 20 pairs and 16 mm channel width was tested for pressure-flowrate performance (Figure 3c). The results show that increasing the applied voltage enhances both pressure and flowrate, with a more pronounced effect on flowrate due to the wider electrodes. The maximum achieved flowrate is 88 mL min^{-1} , as illustrated in Figure 3d.

The response time of the first pump was recorded. Figure 3e presents the response time analysis, showing the pump's ability to reach steady-state pressure within ≈ 0.4 s following a step voltage input. This fast response time is particularly advantageous for applications requiring dynamic flow control. The rapid adaptation to voltage changes highlights the potential of wire electrode EHD pumps for real-time fluidic systems where quick response and adaptability are essential. The flow reversibility of the pump is demonstrated in Figure 3f, where a pump with 20 electrode pairs and a 4 mm channel width is tested under both positive and negative voltages. The results show a symmetrical response, confirming that the pump can reverse the flow direction simply by switching the polarity of the applied voltage. This capability is essential for applications requiring bidirectional flow control, such as soft robotics and thermal management systems.

The power efficiency of liquid EHD pumps depends on both the generated fluidic power and the electric power consumption, which are influenced by various factors, including electrode shape, geometric design, and dielectric fluid properties. In general, the efficiency of EHD pumps is relatively low due to the high electrical resistance of dielectric liquids and energy conversion losses between electrical and fluidic power. Some recent studies have reported efficiency improvements. Xin et al. developed a 3D-printed antistretching EHD pump and reported a maximum efficiency of 0.9%,^[41] while a stretchable EHD pump for wearable thermal devices achieved 0.2% efficiency.^[42] Tang et al. designed a customized EHD pump for a soft robot with an estimated efficiency of 0.4%.^[43] A fiber-shaped EHD pump utilizing wire electrodes demonstrated a maximum efficiency of 2.1% at its maximum length,^[31] while the previous resilient EHD pump reached a maximum of 0.44%.^[38]

Optimization of the pump design can enhance the efficiency of liquid EHD pumps. This can be achieved by adjusting the electrode gap, electrode pair configuration, and channel height. Optimizing these parameters maximizes the electric field in the desired flow direction while minimizing backflow due to electric field components in the opposite direction, thereby improving the overall pumping performance. Kano et al. investigated electrode arrangements for a micropump and reported a maximum efficiency of 0.6%.^[44] Mao et al. optimized electrode patterns and channel height through simulation for an EHD pump used in a rolling robot, reporting an efficiency of 2%.^[45]

We investigated current consumption in designs using different wire diameters while keeping the geometry optimized. It was found that minimizing the electrode surface area, which can be achieved by reducing the wire electrode diameter, helps to reduce unnecessary power loss while still enabling sufficient charge injection. As shown in Figure 3g, four pumps with different wire diameters (0.1, 0.15, 0.2, and 0.3 mm) and the same geometric

configuration ($a = 0.4$ mm, $b = 1.4$ mm) were tested to evaluate current consumption. The results show that current consumption increases with wire diameter. Further investigation into power consumption related to wire electrodes is presented in Note S2, Supporting Information. An inverse relationship between wire electrode diameter and efficiency was observed, as shown in Figure 3h.

Efficiency was also found to vary with applied voltage. It increased with voltage due to enhanced fluidic performance, peaking around 4 kV. Beyond this point, rising electrical losses and saturation effects led to a decrease in efficiency (Figure 3i). The maximum recorded efficiency of our pump was 1.6%, which is more than three times higher than the maximum efficiency of the previous resilient pump (0.44%).^[38] Efficiency can potentially be improved further by employing even smaller wire electrode diameters.

The developed wire pump achieved a maximum pressure of 107 kPa, a maximum flowrate of 88 mL min⁻¹, and a maximum fluidic power of 21.09 mW using the configuration with 80 electrode pairs and a 4 mm channel width. The maximum power density reached 133.49 mW cm⁻³ based on the channel size, 1.334 mW cm⁻³ based on the total pump volume, and 1.232 mW g⁻¹ based on the pump mass. Compared to the previous resilient EHD pump,^[38] the new wire pump design demonstrates substantial performance improvements: over twice the maximum pressure (223%), a 40% increase in maximum flowrate, more than four times the maximum fluidic power (477%), and over double the power density based on channel size (232%). Although the thickness of the new wire pump (4.5 mm) is significantly greater than that of the previous resilient EHD pump (1 mm)—resulting in an increase in both volume and mass—it still achieves a 2% improvement in power density based on total pump size and a 20% increase based on pump mass. Additionally, the overall efficiency improved by more than three times (364%) (Figure 1i). Further details of the performance and power density calculations, as well as a comparison with other EHD pumps, are provided in Note S4, Supporting Information.

2.4. Scalability

To evaluate the scalability of the pump, various pump sizes were fabricated. Increasing the number of electrode pairs is expected to enhance the output pressure, whereas increasing the channel width is expected to improve the flowrate.^[38] The two types of investigations were conducted. The results demonstrate the influence of these parameters on pressure generation, flowrate, fluidic power, and efficiency.

2.4.1. Effect of Electrode Pair Number

The influence of the number of electrode pairs on pump performance was studied using four different pump sizes with 10, 20, 40, and 80 electrode pairs, all with the same channel width of 4 mm, as shown in Figure 4a. This figure illustrates the increasing pump size with additional electrodes. The pressure–voltage characteristics (Figure 4c) indicate that the pressure generated by the pump increases with the number of electrode pairs, following a nonlinear trend. At higher voltages, pumps with a greater

number of electrode pairs exhibit significantly higher pressure due to the cumulative effect of multiple electrode interactions. Similarly, the flowrate–voltage characteristics (Figure 4d) show a slight improvement in flowrate with an increasing number of electrode pairs, confirming that while a higher number of pairs enhances both pressure and flowrate, the effect is more pronounced for pressure.

Scalability in terms of maximum fluidic power and efficiency were examined, as shown in Figure 4e. The fluidic power, represented by the green curve, increases as the number of electrode pairs rises, reaching a maximum at 80 pairs in an almost linear relationship. This result demonstrates that increasing the number of electrode pairs is effective in generating higher fluidic power. The efficiency at 6.5 kV, denoted by the orange curve, exhibits a stable trend for all sizes.

2.4.2. Effect of Channel Width

Figure 4b shows four different wire electrode EHD pumps used to study the effect of channel width, with widths of 2, 4, 8, and 16 mm, highlighting the increasing cross-sectional area of the flow channel. The number of electrode pairs was fixed at 20. The flowrate–voltage characteristics (Figure 4g) reveal that a wider channel results in a higher flowrate, indicating that the volumetric flowrate benefits from the expanded cross-sectional area, allowing more fluid to be transported. The pressure–voltage characteristics (Figure 4f) show that as the channel width increases, pressure generation decreases slightly. This reduction is attributed to increased dielectric losses and flow instabilities that appear in wider channels.^[46] In Figure 4h, fluidic power and efficiency are compared as functions of channel width. The fluidic power increases with channel width, following a nonlinear trend due to the slight decrease in pressure in wider channels. However, efficiency tends to decrease as more current is required to transport a larger volume of liquid at higher flowrates. These results indicate that an optimal channel width exists where the balance between pressure generation and flowrate maximizes overall pump performance.

The scalability analysis highlights that increasing the number of electrode pairs significantly enhances pressure and slightly improves flowrate while maintaining a stable efficiency range. On the other hand, increasing the channel width enhances flowrate but reduces pressure slightly, leading to a tradeoff between these performance parameters. These findings provide essential insights into the design considerations for optimizing EHD pumps based on specific application requirements.

2.5. Discharge Test and Performance Stability

To evaluate the resilience of the wire electrode EHD pump under repeated dielectric discharges, a discharge test was conducted over 50 successive discharges for a wire EHD pump with 20 electrode pairs and a 4 mm channel width. A single discharge test involves gradually increasing the applied voltage in a staircase waveform until dielectric discharge occurs. The results assess the variations in flowrate and voltage.

Figure 5a illustrates the dielectric discharge voltage trends over 50 discharge events, as well as the flowrate performance

Figure 4. The wire EHD pump scalability test. a) Scaling the number of electrode pairs. b) Scaling the channel width. c) Pressure test for wire pumps with different numbers of pairs and a 4 mm channel width. d) Flowrate test for wire pumps with different numbers of pairs and a 4 mm channel width. e) Fluidic power and efficiency for pumps with different numbers of pairs. f) Pressure test for wire pumps with different channel widths and 20 pairs. g) Flowrate test for wire pumps with different channel widths and 20 pairs. h) Fluidic power and efficiency for pumps with different channel widths.

at a voltage of 6.5 kV. The maximum voltage reached for each discharge was recorded (red squares). The discharge voltage exhibits minimal variation, ranging between 6.5 and 10 kV, with an average of 8.53 kV. The flowrate (blue triangles) declines slightly during the early discharges and then remains relatively stable throughout the test, fluctuating around an average of $32.58 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$. The dashed lines represent the trends of flowrate and voltage over time, confirming that the pump maintains stable performance despite repeated electrical discharges.

An image sequence of the wire electrode EHD pump at different stages of the discharge process is shown in Figure 5b.

The first image presents the pump in its initial state before any discharge. The next frame captures the occurrence of a discharge event, where a localized dielectric breakdown is observed. Subsequently, the image shows the aftermath of the discharge, including visible gas bubble formation accompanying the dielectric breakdown. A small black dot appears on the acrylic side of the channel at the discharge site. However, since the electrodes are diagonally separated, this black dot does not form a conductive path between the electrodes of the same pair, allowing the pump to continue functioning despite multiple discharge events. With each discharge, gas generation is observed, producing gas

Figure 5. Resilience test of the wire EHD pump. a) Discharge resilience test over 50 discharges, showing discharge voltage and flowrate performance at 6.5 kV versus discharge number. b) The wire EHD pump with 20 pairs and a 4 mm channel width shown before discharge, during discharge, and after discharge with the generated bubble.

bubbles with high conductivity. If not removed, these bubbles can trigger additional discharges. In this test, the bubbles were manually removed after each discharge before reapplying the voltage.

The flowrate performance at selected discharge intervals (1, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 discharges) as a function of applied voltage is shown in Figure 1e. The curves exhibit an initial decline within the first ten discharges, after which the flowrate–voltage relationship remains stable. Overall, the pump retained 88% of its initial flowrate after 50 discharge events, corresponding to less than 12% performance loss. This slight reduction is attributed to minor substrate blackening near the electrodes that appears after the discharge, which subtly disturbs the electric field, and to microburned fragments and impurities generated in the fluid during repeated discharges, which reduce dielectric strength and ion transport efficiency. Importantly, unlike conventional nonresilient EHD pumps where a single discharge can cause permanent failure, the resilient design confines breakdowns within the dielectric fluid and prevents destructive shorts, ensuring continued stable operation. These findings demonstrate the robustness of the wire electrode EHD pump and its suitability for long-term applications where discharge events are unavoidable. Movie S1, Supporting Information, shows the 50-discharge test followed by continuous operation without the need for cleaning.

2.6. Self-Recovery Mechanism

When a dielectric discharge occurs, a gas bubble is formed. Due to the high conductivity of the generated gases, the bubble will cause an electric discharge as soon as voltage is applied, as it exists between the electrodes. The generated bubbles need to be removed to restore pump functionality. In this section, a fully automatic self-recovery mechanism is proposed to remove the generated bubbles and rapidly restore pump function.

Self-sensing of dielectric discharges can be achieved using a current sensor to monitor the consumed current. When a dielectric discharge occurs, a sudden increase in current consumption is detected. Therefore, a threshold value can be used as an indicator of discharge. When the current reaches this threshold, the controller detects the dielectric discharge and triggers a switching circuit to rapidly alternate the voltage between the main and

auxiliary pumps. This process removes the generated bubbles within a specified time, after which the system restores normal operation of the main pump.

2.6.1. Self-Recovery Mechanism for Continuous Flow

The performance of the self-recovery mechanism was evaluated using a setup consisting of a main pump and an auxiliary pump integrated within the same pump frame. Both pumps have a 4 mm channel width, with the main pump containing 20 electrode pairs and the auxiliary pump containing 10 pairs (Figure 6a). Under normal operating conditions, the main pump runs steadily, generating continuous fluid flow. The applied voltage increases in a step waveform until a dielectric discharge occurs. When this discharge takes place, a sharp rise in current is observed, exceeding the predefined threshold and indicating electrical breakdown. This event triggers the switching mechanism, which immediately activates the auxiliary pump while temporarily deactivating the main pump. The switching process is accomplished via a fast-response high-voltage relay circuit, as shown in Figure S9, Supporting Information, which instantly redirects the voltage to maintain uninterrupted flow operation. The bubble removal phase is evident in the auxiliary pump's voltage profile, where a short activation period of 10 s ensures effective bubble clearance before the system returns to normal operation.

Following the recovery phase, the auxiliary pump stops, and the main pump resumes operation. The automated switching mechanism successfully restores flow without interruption, confirming the effectiveness of the proposed self-recovery strategy. Experimental results demonstrate that the system can autonomously detect dielectric discharges and restore normal operation without external intervention (Figure 6b, Movie S2 Supporting Information), ensuring continuous and reliable pumping performance for soft robotic applications that require uninterrupted flow, such as heat transfer wearable devices.

2.6.2. Self-Recovery Mechanism for Soft Actuators

Soft fluidic actuators are among the most commonly used actuators in soft robotics. Therefore, it is important to introduce

Figure 6. Autorecovery mechanism for continuous flow. a) The main pump with the Auxiliary pump in the same frame. b) Discharge sensing and autorecovery by voltage switching to achieve continuous flow.

a self-recovery mechanism for soft fluidic actuators driven by EHD pumps. For this purpose, a thin McKibben artificial muscle^[26,47] was selected to be tested with the self-recovery wire electrode EHD pump.

Figure 7 demonstrates the functionality of the self-recovery mechanism in ensuring continuous operation of the McKibben artificial muscle driven by the wire electrode EHD pump. The pump is placed in a horizontal position (Figure S11, Supporting Information). If placed vertically, the bubbles would rise due to the low density of the generated gases, allowing passive removal. Instead, the horizontal position traps the bubbles

inside the main pump after discharge. Therefore, the self-recovery mechanism ensures that the generated bubbles are removed regardless of the pump's orientation.

Figure 7 presents a sequence of images illustrating the automatic self-recovery process. Initially, the main pump operates cyclically (Step 1), generating forward flow toward the soft actuator by activating for 1.5 s and deactivating for another 1.5 s. When a dielectric discharge occurs in the main pump (Step 2), the auxiliary pump is activated instantly via the same switching circuit described in the previous section, reversing the flow direction to remove bubbles generated by the discharge (Step 3).

Figure 7. Automatic self-recovery mechanism for soft robotic actuator (McKibben artificial muscle). a) McKibben muscle under different stages of self-recovery operation. b) The main pump and the auxiliary pump in the same frame among different stages of dielectric discharge and recovery. c) Discharge sensing and autorecovery by voltage switching to achieve soft actuator actuation.

The reversed flow directs these bubbles into the dielectric liquid reservoir, preventing their entry into the actuator. Consequently, the actuator remains filled exclusively with dielectric liquid—free of bubbles—throughout operation.

Since the liquid inside the soft actuator is limited, continuous operation of the auxiliary pump would be ineffective, as it would leave bubbles inside the main pump due to the insufficient liquid volume needed to push the bubbles out into the reservoir. Instead, the auxiliary pump oscillates in the opposite direction at a frequency of 1 Hz. This oscillation enables interaction between the limited liquid volume and the actuator's soft body,

effectively dislodging and safely removing bubbles. This process clears the obstruction and restores normal conditions within 10 s. Finally, the main pump resumes operation (Step 4), continuing the actuation of the McKibben artificial muscle (Movie S3, Supporting Information).

This automatic self-recovery mechanism significantly enhances the reliability and robustness of the EHD pump, ensuring uninterrupted soft actuator operation without requiring external intervention. The results confirm that the proposed switching strategy effectively eliminates dielectric discharge-induced failures within a short recovery time, making it suitable for

real-world soft robotics applications where continuous and autonomous function is required.

2.7. EHD Driven Soft Actuator

McKibben artificial muscles generate substantial force while remaining lightweight, making them ideal for flexible and adaptable applications. Their ability to mimic natural muscle movements and inherent compliance allow them to absorb impacts without complex feedback control, which is particularly

beneficial in human-interactive robotics. Thin McKibben artificial muscles share these advantages and have the additional benefit of operating effectively at relatively low pressures, expanding their applicability in wearable and assistive soft robotic devices.^[26] Cacucciolo et al. integrated a thin McKibben muscle with two stretchable EHD pumps, loaded with a 2 g weight, achieving 2.4% contraction in 30 s^[39] as it is maximum full contraction. This response time and energy efficiency require further optimization. The fiber EHD pump was integrated with an inverse hydraulic artificial muscle (IHAM), achieving a high response

Figure 8. Application of the McKibben artificial muscle. a) Muscle stroke with 50 g load mass when 6 kV is applied, along with the corresponding pressure and flowrate values over one cycle. b) Stroke versus applied pressure. c) Stroke values for different applied forces. d) Thin McKibben artificial muscle undergoing four cycles of actuation at 0.33 Hz. e) Muscle response during a 2 s actuation period. f) Strain values under load masses of 0, 5, 25, 50, and 100 g.

time of 1 s.^[31] However, the actuator itself has a complex structure, incorporating a spring mechanism, a wide cross-section, and operating in an inverse mechanism compared to thin McKibben artificial muscles. In this section, a wire electrode EHD pump is integrated and tested to drive a thin McKibben artificial muscle.

The experimental setup, shown in Figure S12, Supporting Information, consists of a thin McKibben artificial muscle connected to a wire EHD pump with 80 pairs and a 4 mm channel width, along with flowrate and pressure sensors for monitoring system performance. The artificial muscle is actuated by the pressurized working fluid generated by the pump, and its stroke is measured under different load conditions. A voltage of 6 kV is applied to drive the pump, enabling fluid transportation through the system.

Figure 8a illustrates the variation of stroke, pressure, flowrate, and voltage over a single cycle at an applied voltage of 6 kV while the actuator is loaded with 50 g. The actuator reached its full contraction (12% strain) in 4.6 s. At the beginning, the flowrate (blue curve) spikes as the actuator rapidly fills with liquid, utilizing the high flowrate generated by the wire electrode EHD pump. As the actuator fills, the flowrate begins to decrease while the EHD pump power is redirected to generate higher pressure (red curve). The stroke curve (green curve) is expected to follow the pressure curve; however, due to the nonlinear elastic characteristics of McKibben actuators, the response is not perfectly proportional. Additionally, friction between the inner tube and the outer sleeve causes the actuator to take longer to fully contract.

The relationship between stroke and applied pressure is presented in Figure 8b while the muscle is unloaded. The plot exhibits a hysteresis effect, where the stroke increases with pressure during muscle inflation and follows a different path during deflation. This characteristic is typical of McKibben artificial muscles due to their nonlinear elastic properties, as well as the dynamic effects of EHDs.

Figure 8c depicts the stroke values for different applied load forces. As the load force increases, the stroke decreases due to the additional resistance, which limits muscle inflation under the same applied pressure. This trend demonstrates the effect of external resistance on the artificial muscle's actuation performance. A cyclic test over four cycles with a 5 g load is shown in Figure 8d. Figure 8e demonstrates the actuator's response over a 2 s period when directly connected to the EHD pump without extensive tubing for measurement. The results indicate that the actuator can achieve 85% of its full contraction in just 2 s. When the voltage is turned off, the actuator returns to its initial position in 0.6 s.

The strain of the artificial muscle under varying loads is shown in Figure 8f. The images correspond to load masses of 0, 5, 25, 50, and 100 g, with the measured strain indicated for each case, ranging between 15% at no load and 10% at 100 g. A decrease in strain is observed as the load increases, confirming the expected behavior of the muscle under external force. A further comparison between this work and^[39] in terms of response time, strain, and force is presented in Table 1. While the present system demonstrates significantly faster actuation and improved strain and force compared to previous integrations, further enhancement is still required. Thin McKibben artificial muscles can achieve up to 27% stroke at 500 kPa, generating a maximum contraction force

Table 1. Comparison of maximum strain, response time, and force of EHD-driven McKibben muscles.

Characteristic	Electrically-driven McKibben muscle ^[39]	This work
Maximum strain (full contraction) [%]	2.4	15
Response time (full contraction) (s)	30	4.6
Response time (85% contraction) [s]	23	2
Maximum force at 0% strain [N]	0.82	4.8

of about 20 N.^[26] Therefore, developing larger and more scalable EHD pumps capable of delivering higher pressures would enable greater strain and force generation, while increasing the flowrate is expected to further improve actuation speed, which may currently be limited by fabrication constraints. Advancing the pump through automated and scalable fabrication processes will be essential for achieving more powerful, efficient, and practical soft robotic and wearable systems.

Movie S4, Supporting Information, demonstrates all the tests performed to evaluate the integration between the muscle and the wire electrode EHD pump. The results indicate that the McKibben artificial muscle successfully responds to the fluidic power generated by the wire EHD pump, demonstrating the system's capability for fluid-driven actuation. These findings provide valuable insights into the integration of EHD-based pumping systems with soft robotic actuators.

3. Conclusion

This work presents a novel resilient wire electrode EHD pump that addresses the critical limitations of previous resilient designs in terms of dielectric discharge vulnerability, scalability, and power density. By employing 0.1 mm copper wire electrodes arranged diagonally within a rigid laser-cut acrylic frame, the proposed pump achieves finer electrode spacing, prevents structural deformation under high pressure, and enables consistent performance even in wider channels. The simplified fabrication method, requiring only laser cutting and assembly from widely available materials, demonstrated excellent reproducibility with a maximum coefficient of variation below 5%, confirming the reliability of the process for scalable production.

Experimental results highlight substantial performance improvements compared to the previous resilient EHD pump, achieving a maximum pressure of 107 kPa, a maximum flowrate of 88 mL min⁻¹, and a maximum fluidic power of 21.09 mW. These values correspond to more than double the power density based on channel volume, and over 20% improvement based on total pump mass, while retaining 88% of the flowrate after 50 consecutive dielectric discharges. The diagonal electrode arrangement and rigid structural design ensure that discharge events generate only temporary fluid bubbles rather than permanent conductive paths, significantly enhancing operational durability.

In addition to its inherent resilience, the pump was integrated with a fully automated self-recovery mechanism that instantaneously switches operation to an auxiliary pump upon

discharge detection. This enables continuous and uninterrupted flow without external intervention, effectively restoring the main pump's performance after each event. Integration with a McKibben artificial muscle demonstrated the practical applicability of the system, achieving a contraction time of 2 s—ten times faster than previous EHD-driven implementations—while producing 15% strain and 4.8 N of force at zero strain.

The combination of compact size, high performance, resilience to dielectric breakdown, automated recovery, and compatibility with soft actuators positions the proposed EHD pump as a strong candidate for next-generation wearable and assistive robotics. Future work will prioritize developing an automated fabrication process to replace manual wire winding, which will further enhance scalability, precision, and production speed. Another promising direction is the adoption of thinner and lighter base materials, which can significantly increase both the volumetric power density and the power density per unit weight. Moreover, future efforts will focus on system-level integration, including compact battery-powered driver circuits, improved insulation, and current-monitoring safety features, to enable reliable and user-safe operation in practical wearable applications. These advances will pave the way for fully portable robotic platforms in applications such as wearable rehabilitation devices.

4. Experimental Section

Pump Performance Characterization: The dielectric fluid used in this evaluation is Novec 7300 from 3M. Low conductivity is crucial for effective EHD pumping ($<10^{-7} \text{ S m}^{-1}$). Novec 7300 has a dielectric constant of 6.1 and a conductivity of 10^{-9} S m^{-1} . Additionally, it is well-suited for soft robotic applications due to its high thermal conductivity, ultralow toxicity, nonflammability, zero flash point, zero ozone depletion potential, and a boiling point of 76 °C. Fresh fluid is used for each pump test.

A specially designed fluid circuit is employed to characterize the pumps, as shown in Figure S12, Supporting Information. The setup includes a fluid reservoir, a motorized pinch valve (Resolution Air MPPV-4), a pressure sensor (KEYENCE GP-M001T), a flowrate sensor (KEYENCE FD-XS1) with a controller and display unit (KEYENCE FD-XA1), and the wire pump itself. The sensors are calibrated prior to measurement. A high-voltage source for the evaluation is provided by Matsusada AMP High Voltage Amplifier. Data acquisition is performed using a KEYENCE NR-500. To control the applied voltage and the pinch valve, an NI-9264 module mounted on a cDAQ-9178 chassis from NI Instruments is used. A LabVIEW program is employed to control both the voltage and the pinch motor while simultaneously collecting data for pressure, flowrate, and current.

Pressure and Flowrate Characterization: For the pressure versus voltage and flowrate versus voltage curves, the voltage is increased in steps to create a staircase waveform. The process starts at 0 kV for 10 s, followed by increments of 0.5 kV for 30 s each, until the discharge voltage is reached.

In the pressure test, the pinch valve is fully closed, blocking the flow and causing the pressure to reach its maximum value. Conversely, in the flowrate test, the pinch valve is fully open, allowing the flowrate to reach its maximum. Each point on the flowrate and pressure curves represents the average value of the collected data over a 30 s interval. The standard deviation of the average is represented by error bars.

Pressure-Flowrate Curves: The pinch valve is used to generate pressure-flowrate curves (pQ curves). Initially, the valve is fully open, allowing the flowrate to reach its maximum. Then, the valve is gradually closed using micro-stepping, controlled by a LabVIEW program over a duration of 10 min. During this process, the flowrate decreases while the pressure gradually increases until the valve is completely closed, at which point the pressure reaches its maximum value. This procedure is repeated for different voltage levels.

Discharge-Discharge Test: In the discharge resilience evaluation, the flowrate test is performed over 50 discharges. During each test, the discharge voltage is recorded. The minimum discharge voltage observed across the 50 discharges is used as a reference voltage to assess changes in flowrate performance.

Self-Recovery Test for Continuous Flow: For the self-recovery continuous flow experiment, the CB101 high-voltage amplifier is used as the power source. This amplifier features built-in voltage and current sensing. The current sensor is utilized for discharge recognition: when the current value exceeds a predefined threshold, it triggers the controller to switch the high voltage to the auxiliary pump. The auxiliary pump starts operating simultaneously with the discharge and runs for 10 s to remove the bubble from the main pump. Afterward, the voltage is switched back to the main pump, enabling continuous flow without any interruption in operation.

Two high-voltage switching relays (OR-100-10 kV High Voltage Opto-Relay) from HVM Technology, Inc., USA are employed to switch the high voltage between the main and auxiliary pumps (Figure S9, Supporting Information). A LabVIEW program is used for control; alternatively, an Arduino can also be used for this process.

Self-Recovery Test for Soft Actuator: A McKibben artificial muscle is used as a soft robotic actuator. The experimental setup is shown in Figure S10, Supporting Information. The wire electrode pump consists of two pumps within the same device frame: a main pump with 100 electrode pairs and a 10 mm channel width, and an auxiliary pump with ten electrode pairs and a 10 mm channel width. A Matsusada AMP High Voltage Amplifier is used as the power source. The applied voltage is controlled to oscillate at 0.33 Hz at 6 kV and continues until a dielectric discharge occurs.

When a dielectric discharge is detected, the same switching circuit described for the continuous flow self-recovery mechanism is used to transfer the voltage to the auxiliary pump. The auxiliary pump oscillates at 1 Hz to remove bubbles by pushing them in pulses in the opposite direction of the normal flow. After 10 s, ensuring complete bubble removal, the power is switched back to the main pump to resume normal operation.

EHD Driven Soft Actuator: To measure the pressure and flowrate of the McKibben artificial muscle's performance, the muscle is connected to the experimental setup shown in Figure S11, Supporting Information. The voltage is applied as a step input, and the muscle's motion stroke is tracked using a ruler and recorded using motion tracking through a visual camera.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

electrohydrodynamics, high-power density, McKibben muscle, resilient, self-recovery, soft actuator, soft robotics

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